

Bulk superconductivity at $T_c = 0.79$ K in $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrBi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$: An AC-susceptibility investigation

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Abstract:

$\text{Eu}_2\text{SrBi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$ and $\text{EuSr}_2\text{Bi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$ have been synthesized [1] and investigated by recently designed a fully automated AC susceptometer for milli-kelvin temperature in Dynacool PPMS [2]. They are derivatives of the novel parent compound $\text{Eu}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$, [2] which shows superconductivity at 1.5 K [3] and is different from other BiS_2 superconductors in that it is an intrinsic superconductor; namely, no external doping is required to induce superconductivity (SC). As a result of Sr-substitution at the Eu-sites in $\text{Eu}_3\text{Bi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$, T_c was initially found to decrease from 1.5 K to 0.87 K for ($x = 0.5$) and then to 0.48 K in $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrBi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$ [3] and no sign of SC can be detected on further increasing Sr content at $x=2$ down to 0.3 K in $\text{EuSr}_2\text{Bi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$ [3]. Results of our new magnetic measurements show $T_c \sim 0.79$ K [4] in $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrBi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$ which represents a substantial enhancement in T_c as compared to $T_c = 0.48$ K reported earlier. This suggests an improvement of the quality of the sample. The decreased Eu^{3+} population resulting in corresponding decrease in charge carrier density, may be the main reason for the suppression of superconductivity [4]. Here we report [5] temperature dependence of the AC susceptibility $\chi_{ac}(T)$ of $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrBi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$ superconductor. AC susceptibility is measured with an AC drive field with frequency of 4125 Hz and amplitude of 0.02 Oe. The DC applied field was initially fixed at zero to check the superconducting transition temperature and then increased to 10 Oe and then goes up to 440 Oe to check the AC losses in the mixed state. Both the real (χ') and imaginary (χ'') parts of the AC susceptibility were measured. χ' shows a sharp diamagnetic transition at ~ 0.79 K confirming the bulk superconductivity in $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrBi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$. On the other hand, χ'' exhibited a single, sharp, positive peak at around the same temperature. The presence of a single sharp peak in χ'' is indicative of better coupling of the superconducting grains in the studied $\text{Eu}_2\text{SrBi}_2\text{S}_4\text{F}_4$ superconductor. Further, under an applied DC field upto 440 Oe, the χ' diamagnetic transition shifts to a lower temperature 0.29 K, and the corresponding χ'' peak is broadened and shifted to the same lower temperature. This is usual for a type-II superconductor. At a DC field of 440 Oe, neither χ' nor χ'' showed transitions, which is indicative of rapid suppression of the superconductivity.

Reference:

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2. Amann A. *et al.* IEEE Trans, Appl, Supercond. DOI: 10.1109/TASC.2016.2639480 (2016)
3. Zhai, H. F. *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 136, 15386 (2014).